

C and A and B parameters of Jone-Dole equation, of different solutions involving ascorbic acid.

analysis and infrared spectra. The following α,β -unsaturated ketones were synthesised :

References

1. H. R. ROSENBERG, "Chemistry and Physiology of Vitamins", Interscience, New York, 1945, p. 130.
2. M. V. KAULGUD, H. G. DOLE and K. S. M. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, 16, 955.
3. G. K. WARD and F. J. MILLERO, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, 3, 431.
4. S. BHANDARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 88.
5. R. L. BLOKHRA and Y. P. SEHGAL, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, 5, 499.
6. S. P. MOULIK, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1973, 18, 981.
7. D. P. SHOEMAKER and C. W. GARLAND, "Experiments in Physical Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1967, p. 130.
8. R. L. BLOKHRA and M. L. PARMAR, *Aust J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 1407.
9. R. L. BLOKHRA and Y. P. SEHGAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 998.
10. R. L. BLOKHRA, Y. P. SEHGAL and V. P. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 505.
11. R. M. FUOSS and C. A. KRAVSS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2387.
12. N. BJERRUM, *Det. Kgl. Danske. Vidensk.*, 1926, 9, 2.
13. B. B. OWEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1393.
14. S. GLASSTONE, "An Introduction to Electrochemistry", Van Nostrand-Reinhold, New York, 1942, p. 60.
15. G. JONES and M. DOLF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 57, 2050.
16. J. PADOVA in "Water in Aqueous Solutions", ed. R. A. HORNE, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 109.

(I)

- 1 ; R = C₆H₄CH₃-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 2 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 3 ; R = C₆H₄Br-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = OH, C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 4 ; R = C₆H₄Cl-p, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 5 ; R = OH(CH₂)₃, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 6 ; R = C₆H₁₁, R₁ = OH, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 7 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = OH, C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 8 ; R = C₆H₄NO₂-m, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 9 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 10 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-m, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = OH, CH₂CN
- 11 ; R = C₆H₄CH₃-p, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₂C₆H₅, R₃ = CH₂CH₂CN
- 12 ; R = C₆H₄CH₃-p, R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = C₂H₅
- 13 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = C₂H₅
- 14 ; R = OH(CH₂)₃, R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = C₂H₅

(II)

- 15 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = NO₂
- 16 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = Br
- 17 ; R = C₆H₄Cl-p, R₁ = Br
- 18 ; R = C₆H₅, R₁ = Br
- 19 ; R = C₆H₄Br-p, R₁ = Br
- 20 ; R = C₆H₄OCH₃-p, R₁ = H

Synthesis of some α,β -Unsaturated-ketones.

Part-I

VIJAY SHANKER SINGH, S. C. GOEL**

and

S. M. L. GUPTA*

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 4 August 1981, accepted 24 December 1985

VARIOUS α,β -unsaturated ketones have been synthesised by Claisen reaction¹, which may be useful as insect-attractants and possess antifungal activity.

Some ketones like anisylacetone² and benzyl acetone³ etc., have been found to be useful as insect-attractants and possess antifungal activity as well. With this aim in view, a number of α,β -unsaturated ketones have been synthesised by Claisen reaction. The synthesis of such ketones (1 and 2) was carried out by condensing aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic or aromatic ketones in presence of 5% ethanolic alkali followed by continuous stirring with a mechanical stirrer. The ketones, so separated, were purified and characterised by elemental

Experimental

All the α,β -unsaturated ketones (1-20) were synthesised by treating one mole each of the corresponding aromatic aldehydes with aliphatic or aromatic ketones in 5% ethanolic sodium hydroxide, and stirring for 3 h. The solids were separated by filtration and crystallised from alcohol; while liquids were extracted with ether, washed with water, solvent distilled off, the residue so obtained was a thin syrupy liquid, which could not be distilled even under reduced pressure in each case. The solids were characterised by their m.ps., elemental analyses, infrared spectra and preparation of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, while liquids were characterised by the preparation of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, elemental analyses and infrared spectra of the latter.

All the data are given in Table 1.

** Chemical Laboratory, J. K. Tyre Cord. Ltd., Kota, Rajasthan.

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.) N	$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	DNP, m p °C
1	91	124	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2$	7.00 (7.10)	1 165	191
2	66.9	115	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	6.52 (6.82)	1 665	195
3	82	105	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{OBrN}_2$	6.01 (6.10)	1 660	207
4	72	126	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{OCIN}_2$	6.44 (6.76)	1 655	179
5	66	Thin syrupy liquid	$\text{DNP-C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	15.84 (15.96)	1 655	156
6	66	Thin syrupy liquid	$\text{DNP-C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	15.03 (15.16)	1 660	193
7	80	124 ^c	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2$	7.01 (7.38)	1 660	189
8	65	100	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	9.98 (10.21)	1 660	149
9	68	105	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2$	7.26 (7.65)	1 660	120
10	89	96	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	6.85 (7.07)	1 665	210
11	76	134	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2$	7.01 (7.36)	1 650	178
12	69	102	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ON}$	— (4.77)	1 650	104
13	79	Thin syrupy liquid	$\text{DNP-C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	15.02 (15.25)	1 665	205
14	88	Thin syrupy liquid	$\text{DNP-C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	16.11 (16.47)	1 660	210
15	92	173	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2\text{Br}^a$	3.20 (3.70)	1 650	Semi 194
16	81	176	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2^b$	—	1 670	232
17	78	174	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{ClBr}_2^c$	—	1 655	Semi 193
18	86	158	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2^d$	—	1 660	241
19	82	171	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2^e$	—	1 650	202
20	81	188	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{Br}^f$	—	1 660	160

^a Br, 20.98 (21.16). ^b C, 46.01 (46.60), H, 2.34 (2.91); Br, 38.12 (38.89). ^c C, 69.98 (70.31); H, 3.02 (3.51); Cl, 13.12 (13.67). ^d C, 80.98 (81.08); H, 4.03 (4.50). ^e C, 59.41 (59.80); H, 2.19 (2.99); Br, 26.18 (26.57). ^f C, 57.12 (57.65); H, 3.06 (3.90); Br, 23.89 (24.02).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the State C.S.I.R., U.P., for providing necessary grant and a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them, and to the Principal, Agra College, for providing facilities.

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Thiazolidinones

MANGAT RAI*, B. S. DHIR and P. S. KALSI

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

and

R. C. SHARMA and J. S. JHOOTY

Department of Plant Pathology, Punjab Agricultural University Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 12 October 1984, revised 30 August 1985, accepted 18 June 1986

References

1. CLAISEN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1881, **14**, 2471.
2. W. E. BARTHEL, N. GREEN, I. KRISER and L. F. STEINER, *Science*, 1957, **126**, 654; C. W. SABROSTY, U. S. Dept. Agr., Entomol. Research Div., Private Communication, 1957; S. L. ALLMAN, Dept. of Agr., Sydney, New South Wales, Australia, Private Communication, 1957.
3. D. SCHNEIDER and Z. VERGLEICH, *Physiol.*, 1957, **40**, 841; S. H. HUTNER, H. M. KAPLAN and E. V. ENZMANN, *Am. Naturalist*, 1937, **71**, 575.

4-Thiazolidinones have been reported to possess antifungal activity¹⁻³. The presence of hydroxy-substituted phenyl group is shown to increase the activity of the parent compound^{4,5}. Here the synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones from 4-hydroxybenzal-anilines and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzal-anilines^{1,6} and evaluation of the products as fungicides are reported.

Reaction of thioglycolic acid (2) with 4-hydroxybenzal-anilines and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzal-anilines (1) under Surrey's experimental conditions^{1,7}